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The impact of commercial hunting tourism on the financial autonomy of rural territorial communities in the context of post-war recovery

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Abstract. Current challenges in the socio-economic development of rural territorial communities, driven by the consequences of military actions, necessitate the search for effective mechanisms for generating local revenues based on the use of natural resource potential. Particular importance is attached to integrating hunting management into the tourism sector as a tool for diversifying economic activity and enhancing the financial capacity of territories. The purpose of the study is to determine the role of commercially oriented use of hunting resources in generating income and ensuring the financial sustainability of rural territorial communities in the context of post-war recovery. The methodological basis of the study includes methods of system analysis, comparison, generalization, structural-logical and statistical analysis, which enabled the assessment of the resource, institutional, and economic components of hunting management, as well as the identification of the relationship between tourism activity and the financial performance of territories. The study results indicate that the existing resource base of hunting grounds, combined with a stable institutional structure, creates preconditions for the development of specialized tourism products. Regional differentiation in the

efficiency of potential utilization has been identified, determined by the level of infrastructure development, security conditions, and the degree of integration into the tourism market. It is substantiated that transforming hunting activities into a comprehensive service product ensures the formation of a multi-channel income system, generates a multiplier effect on the local economy, and contributes to strengthening the financial autonomy of communities. A phased approach to the development of this sector is proposed, covering institutional, infrastructural, service, and marketing components. The practical significance lies in the possibility of applying the proposed approach and analytical results by local self-government bodies to develop effective territorial development strategies, expand revenue sources, and strengthen the financial sustainability of rural territorial communities.

Keywords: rural territorial communities, financial sustainability, local revenues, natural resource potential, hunting management, tourism services, economic diversification, post-war recovery.

Вплив комерційного мисливського туризму на фінансову автономію сільських територіальних громад в умовах повоєнного відновлення

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Анотація. Сучасні виклики соціально-економічного розвитку сільських територіальних громад, що зумовлені наслідками воєнних дій, актуалізують пошук ефективних механізмів формування локальних доходів на основі використання природно-ресурсного потенціалу. Особливого значення набуває інтеграція мисливського господарства у сферу туризму як інструменту диверсифікації економічної діяльності та підвищення фінансової спроможності територій. Метою дослідження є визначення ролі комерційно

орієнтованих форм використання мисливських ресурсів у формуванні доходів і забезпеченні фінансової стійкості сільських територіальних громад в умовах повоєнного відновлення. Методологічну основу дослідження становлять методи системного аналізу, порівняння, узагальнення, структурно-логічного та статистичного аналізу, що дозволили оцінити ресурсну, інституційну та економічну складові функціонування мисливського господарства, а також виявити взаємозв'язок між туристичною активністю та фінансовими результатами територій. У результаті дослідження визначено, що наявна ресурсна база мисливських угідь у поєднанні зі стабільною інституційною структурою створює передумови для розвитку спеціалізованих туристичних продуктів. Виявлено регіональну диференціацію ефективності використання потенціалу, що зумовлена рівнем розвитку інфраструктури, безпековими умовами та ступенем інтеграції у туристичний ринок. Обґрунтовано, що трансформація мисливської діяльності у комплексний сервісний продукт забезпечує формування багатоканальної системи доходів, мультиплікативний ефект для місцевої економіки та сприяє зміцненню фінансової автономії громад. Запропоновано поетапний підхід до розвитку цього напрямку, що охоплює інституційні, інфраструктурні, сервісні та маркетингові складові. Практична цінність дослідження полягає у можливості використання запропонованого підходу та аналітичних результатів органами місцевого самоврядування для формування ефективних стратегій розвитку територій, розширення джерел доходів та зміцнення фінансової стійкості сільських територіальних громад.

Ключові слова: сільські територіальні громади, фінансова стійкість, локальні доходи, природно-ресурсний потенціал, мисливське господарство, туристичні послуги, диверсифікація економіки, повоєнне відновлення.

Problem statement. Modern transformation processes in Ukraine's economy, driven by the consequences of military operations, exacerbate the problem of ensuring the financial capacity of rural territorial communities. The limitations of traditional sources of income, the reduction in economic activity, migration processes and the destruction of infrastructure create the need to find new, adaptive mechanisms to fill local budgets and stimulate the development of territories. Under such conditions, the effective use of local natural resource potential as a basis for the development of alternative sources of income becomes particularly important [1]. One such area is hunting tourism, which should be considered not only as a recreational activity but also as an economic tool capable of generating multi-channel financial flows. Its specificity lies in the combination of hunting with tourism infrastructure and service activities, which creates added value and multiplies the local economy's impact [2, p. 58]. In this context, hunting tourism can serve as an effective tool for diversifying rural communities' income, promoting the development of small businesses, increasing employment and strengthening financial autonomy. In post-war reconstruction, the role of such niche areas is growing, as they enable rapid activation of economic activity with available resources, at minimal investment cost. The use of hunting grounds in combination with tourist services creates the prerequisites for the formation of sustainable models of territorial development, focused on local advantages and market demand.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A review of modern scientific approaches to the development of tourism, the use of natural resources, and the financial viability of territories enables a comprehensive assessment of the potential for integrating hunting tourism into the system of local economic development. The works of Y. Geng et al. reveal the interdisciplinary nature of sustainable rural tourism as a tool for combining economic development and environmental balance [3]. The study by P. Gabryjończyk et al. emphasizes the role of rural tourism as a key area of economic recovery in war-torn areas [4, p. 47]. At the same time, M. Roman et al. emphasize the importance of innovation and digitalization in

increasing the efficiency of the tourism sector [5, p. 538]. The economic aspects of hunting tourism are discussed in detail in the works of M. Kalábová et al., who show its significant contribution to the national economy [6], and J. D. Goergen et al., who substantiate the dependence of income on the resource base and tourism activity [7]. The socio-economic effects on communities are revealed in the study by P. van der Merwe and E. Slabbert, who emphasize the multicomponent impact of hunting tourism on the development of rural areas [8, p. 139]. Certain aspects of the organization and development of the natural resource base are highlighted in the works of V. Skliar et al., who emphasize the importance of biodiversity and the impact of anthropogenic activities [9, p. 14], as well as in the works of V. Sklyar and Y. Sklyar, who considered the role of the nature reserve fund in preserving ecosystems and forming an ecological network [10, p. 62]. In turn, I. Slypko et al. emphasize the need to apply adaptive approaches to natural resource management in conditions of limited data and military challenges [11, p. 141]. The study by A. Iutkina considers the competitiveness of the tourism product in the context of digital transformation and emphasizes the role of flexible pricing and service differentiation [12]. The regional dimension of tourism development is presented in the work of Y. Tiutiunnyk et al., which demonstrate the impact of crisis factors on the industry's financial results [1]. At the same time, O. Trachuk substantiates the importance of the cluster approach and digital solutions for increasing the competitiveness of the tourism sector [13, p. 185]. The ecological and management aspects of hunting are reflected in the study of O. Kratiuk et al., which emphasizes the need for an ecosystem approach [14, p. 292], as well as in the work of A. Marchuk et al., which emphasizes the importance of biotechnical measures and land protection [15, p. 17]. Additionally, the study of N. Boretska and G. Krapivina substantiates the feasibility of using cluster analysis for strategic management of tourist and recreational areas [2, p. 57]. The generalization of scientific approaches indicates the feasibility of combining resource potential, tourist infrastructure and innovative and institutional mechanisms to develop an effective model for the

development of hunting tourism as a factor in the financial sustainability of rural territorial communities.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite significant research in the field of rural and hunting tourism, several important aspects remain insufficiently disclosed. In particular, scientific works mainly focus either on the environmental management of hunting resources or on general issues of tourism development, while their integration into the context of building financial sustainability for rural territorial communities is covered only fragmentarily. The issue of transforming the hunting economy into a complex tourism product with clearly defined revenue channels remains insufficiently researched. In addition, there is no systematic analysis of the relationship between the resource base, the level of tourism infrastructure, and the actual financial income of communities, especially accounting for regional differences and the influence of military factors. This limits the possibilities of forming effective models for using existing potential. The actualization of these aspects necessitates the development of a holistic approach to the use of the hunting economy as a resource for territories. Special attention is required to study its transformation into a tourism product capable of diversifying income and increasing the financial capacity of rural territorial communities.

Formulation of the objectives of the article. The purpose of the study is to determine the role of commercial hunting tourism as a tool for generating income and strengthening the financial stability of rural territorial communities in the conditions of post-war recovery.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The development of commercial hunting tourism depends directly on the presence of a well-developed economic and resource base of the hunting economy, which includes both quantitative characteristics of business entities and spatial parameters of the use of hunting grounds. It is the hunting economy that acts as the primary infrastructural basis for the formation of a tourism product, since it provides access to natural

resources [10, p. 63], organization of the hunting process, related services and biodiversity management [9, p. 16]. In this context, it is important to analyze the dynamics of enterprise operations in the hunting sector, which allows us to assess the industry's institutional capacity and its adaptation to economic and security challenges.

The full-scale war had a significant impact on the functioning of the hunting industry in Ukraine, leading to the loss of territory, restricted access to hunting grounds, disruption of logistical and management ties, and a decrease in investment activity in the industry. At the same time, in relatively safe regions, the preservation and partial restoration of hunting entities' activities are observed, creating the prerequisites for using this sector as a tool for the economic activation of rural territorial communities in the post-war period [1]. Changes in the number of operating entities in the field of hunting reflect not only trends in the industry's development, but also broader transformation processes in the economy, in particular, the impact of military operations, territorial losses, a reduction in the resource base, and a decrease in investment activity. At the same time, the restoration or stabilization of the number of such enterprises may indicate the preservation of the basic potential for the further development of hunting tourism, especially in rural communities, where hunting grounds are one of the few available natural assets for economic use. To assess the institutional dynamics of the hunting economy as a basis for the development of commercial hunting tourism, it is advisable to analyze changes in the number of operating enterprises in this sector during key periods of Ukraine's development (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Trends in the number of active enterprises in the hunting sector (NACE Rev. 2, code 01.70) in Ukraine, units

Source: based on [16]

Data analysis indicates clear stages in the development of the hunting industry in Ukraine. Starting from 2019, the dynamics of the development of the hunting industry is characterized by sharp fluctuations: in 2022, the number of entities decreased to 279 units under the influence of military operations, while in 2023, a partial recovery to 368 units was recorded, which indicates the preservation of the basic potential of the industry. Regional analysis confirms the uneven development: leading positions are maintained by regions with a sufficient resource base and a relatively stable security situation (Chernihiv – 40 units, Mykolaiv – 32, Kyiv – 31), while front-line territories suffered the greatest losses (Donetsk – from 13 to 2 units in 2022 with further recovery to 9; Kherson – actual cessation of activity in 2022). In some regions (1–2 entities), a low level of institutional presence remains. In general, despite a significant reduction in 2022, the industry has retained its organizational foundations and is showing signs of recovery, creating the prerequisites for its further transformation into a commercially oriented tourism segment.

In view of this, the next stage of the study is to analyze the resource and institutional base of the hunting industry in Ukraine (table 1).

Table 1

Resource and institutional base of the hunting industry of Ukraine, 2023–2025

Indicator	2023	2024	2025
Area of hunting grounds, million ha	approx. 39.0	38.8	35.9
Share of the country's territory, %	approx. 65.0	64.0	59.5
Number of hunting grounds users, units	approx. 1100	approx. 1100	approx. 1130
Lands provided by the State Forestry Agency, million ha	23.0	24.3	22.0
Lands of enterprises of the State Forest Agency, million ha	4.0	4.0	3.6
Lands of other users, million ha	12.0	10.5	10.3

Source: compiled according to [17]

As calculations show, Ukraine's hunting economy retains significant spatial and resource potential. In 2023, the area of hunting grounds was about 39.0 million ha (approximately 65% of the country's territory), while in 2025 it decreased to 35.9 million ha (–7.9%) and the share of the territory to 59.5%, reflecting the impact of military factors. At the same time, the number of users remains stable – about 1,100 units with a slight increase to 1,130, which confirms the preservation of the institutional basis of the industry. The dominant role is played by the Ukrainian Society of Hunters and Fishermen (over 22 million ha), but the segment of other users (over 10 million ha) remains significant, providing a basis for the development of commercially oriented models.

In such conditions, it is important to assess the industry's efficiency, in particular with respect to income generation and administrative activity (table 2).

Table 2

Financial and administrative results of the functioning of the hunting economy of Ukraine in 2023–2025

Indicator	2023	2024	2025
Revenues to local budgets from administrative services, thousand UAH	229.5	672.2	906.6
Number of administrative services provided, units	18 021	57 181	74 790

Indicator	2023	2024	2025
Licenses issued for hunting animals, million UAH	–	3.43	4.21
Licenses sold to hunters, million UAH	–	1.329	2.825
Number of protocols for violation of hunting rules, units	656	611	About 300

Source: built according to [17]

These tables indicate a gradual recovery of the sector, as reflected in increased service numbers and budget revenues, confirming the trend towards economic activation. Revenues to local budgets from administrative services increased from 229.5 thousand UAH in 2023 to 906.6 thousand UAH in 2025 (almost 4 times), and the number of services provided – from 18,021 to 74,790 units, which indicates an increase in demand and a revival of activity in the field of hunting. At the same time, the expansion of licensing activities confirms the growth of the economic component: the volume of issued licenses increased from 3.43 to 4.21 million UAH (+22.7%), and their implementation more than doubled, from 1.329 to 2.825 million UAH. The reduction in the number of violations (from 656 to about 300) also indicates a certain streamlining of the industry's operations. At the same time, the development of hunting is constrained by systemic restrictions, among which the key ones are military operations, mining of territories, temporary occupation, epizootic risks and significant regional differentiation. This narrows the potential for full use of the resource base and reduces the industry's overall efficiency.

Under such conditions, hunting, despite generating certain budget revenues, does not fully realize its economic potential. Much wider opportunities for rural territorial communities open up with the integration of hunting activities into the sphere of tourism, where they are transformed into a complex service product. Such a product covers not only the organization of hunting but also related services, including accommodation, catering, transport and recreational support, thereby creating added value at the local level. Therefore, it is important to assess the relationship between the existing resource base of the hunting industry and the actual volumes of tourism revenues, which serve as an indicator of economic activity and

financial capacity of regions (table 3).

Table 3

Interrelationship between the resource base of the hunting industry and the dynamics of tourism revenues in the regions of Ukraine for 2023–2024

Region	Hunting entities, units, 2023	Tourism revenues, UAH million		Level of potential utilization	Impact on the financial capacity of communities
		2023	2024		
Lviv	28	70.0	95.9	High	Sustainable growth in community income
Ivano-Frankivsk	10	34.2	73.1	High	Active diversification of the economy
Kyiv	31	50.0	58.7	High	High level of revenues
Odesa	24	18.9	28.2	Average	Potential underutilized
Poltava	25	8.3	14.4	Average	Generation of additional income
Chernihiv	40	2.0	3.4	Low	Poor realization of potential
Donetsk	9	1.5	2.6	Critically low	Limited financial role
Kherson	4	0.4	0.6	Critically low	Virtually no effect
Zaporizhzhia	5	3.0	3.8	Low	Partial recovery

Source: summarized from [16; 18]

In most regions, positive dynamics in tourism revenues are observed, particularly in Lviv (+25.9 million UAH) and Ivano-Frankivsk (+38.9 million UAH), indicating an active recovery of the tourism sector and an increase in its role in regional income formation. At the same time, in a number of regions, there is a disproportion between the resource base and the actual results of its use. Thus, in the Chernihiv region, with 40 hunting entities, the volume of tourism revenues in 2024 is only 3.4 million UAH, which indicates not only an insufficient level of integration of natural resource potential into the tourism market, but also a significant impact of security restrictions, in particular in border areas, where economic and tourist activities are limited. Such trends confirm that the mere presence of hunting grounds and business entities does not provide an economic effect without the development of infrastructure, service components and organizational mechanisms for commercialization.

Given the gradual restoration of tourist activity in Ukraine, a favorable environment is emerging for the development of specialized forms of tourism focused on local resources. In this context, hunting tourism can be considered as a niche, but economically promising segment, capable of providing additional sources of income for rural territorial communities, especially in conditions of limited alternative areas of economic activity. Generalization of the main characteristics of hunting tourism as a commercial product allows us to specify its economic essence, service structure and potential for generating added value (table 4). The data presented indicate that the basic elements of the market for commercial hunting services have already been established in Ukraine, extending beyond traditional hunting as a separate activity. Hunting tourism is acquiring the features of a complex service product, which includes not only the direct organization of hunting, but also a wide range of related services - hunter support, transport, accommodation, food, trophy processing and additional recreational activities.

Table 4

Commercial characteristics of the hunting tourism product in Ukraine

Main types of services	Format	Base price of the organization	Estimated cost of the trophy / tour	Additional services
«Polissya»				
Deer, wild boar, roe deer, bird and fishing	Individual and collective	4,000 UAH individually; 500 UAH collectively	Deer 15,000–40,000 UAH; wild boar 1,100–12,000 UAH; roe deer 2,500–6,500 UAH	Jester service, transport, chasers, parking and meat sale
«Rokytno»				
Wild boar, spotted deer, roe deer, groundhog, duck	Individual and herd	500 UAH collectively; 1,000–2,000 UAH individual	Wild boar 4,000–14,000 UAH; roe deer 3,000 UAH; deer 14,900–46,500 UAH	Guide, transfer, accommodation, security, trophy processing
Andrushivske farm				
Deer, roe deer, fallow deer, mouflon, fur-	Individual and collective	1,000 UAH huntsman services	Deer 30,000–100,000 UAH; roe deer 4,400–7,400 UAH;	Dog, buggy, tractor, horse-drawn transport,

Main types of services	Format	Base price of the organization	Estimated cost of the trophy / tour	Additional services
bearing animal, game birds			wild boar 4,600–16,600 UAH	feathering
Carpathian hunting tour				
Red deer hunting	Tour 3–7 days	1,800 euros for a 3-day tour	Licenses and documents for the trophy are paid separately	Accommodation, meals, jeeps, translator, trophy delivery

Source: created by [19–22]

An important characteristic is the presence of different formats and price segments – from local collective hunts with a relatively low cost to individual premium-level tours (in particular in the Carpathian region), which are focused on solvent demand, including foreign clients. Such differentiation indicates the gradual formation of market mechanisms, the diversification of supply and the possibility of adapting the product to different consumer groups. Therefore, hunting tourism in Ukraine already functions as a multi-component market product, capable of generating added value not only within the hunting economy but also in related activities. This creates the prerequisites for spreading the economic effect to a wider range of local economic entities, including the service sector, transport, trade and small business, which is especially important for ensuring the financial sustainability of rural territorial communities. In this context, a detailed analysis of the income-generating channels from commercial hunting tourism and their role in the structure of local budgets and communities' economies is appropriate (table 5).

Table 5

Channels of income generation from commercial hunting tourism and their importance for rural territorial communities

Channel of income	Service / payment	Economic effect on the community
Organization of hunting	Fee for participation in individual or collective hunting	Direct income of business entities
Trophy payments	Payment for captured animals depends on the species, weight and trophy quality	Formation of the main part of the revenue
Licenses and	Hunter's license, control cards, permits,	Revenues to local budgets

Channel of income	Service / payment	Economic effect on the community
administrative services	documents	
Support and service	Gamers, guides, chasers, translators, security	Job creation
Transport services	Rent of jeeps, buggies, tractors, other, transfer	Revenues of the local service sector
Accommodation and food	Hunting bases, cottages, manors and local cuisine	Multiplicative effect for the hospitality sector
Additional activities	Fishing, shooting range, sauna, jeeping and other recreational services	Diversification of the local tourism product
Product sales and trophy processing	Meat, processing, trophy preparation	Expansion of the local value chain

Source: compiled by the author

Thus, unlike traditional hunting, where the financial impact is mainly limited to license and administrative fees, integration into the tourism market creates a multi-channel income system. The main source of revenue is organizing hunting and trophy payments, which are the primary sources of income for business entities. At the same time, related services – support, transport, accommodation, food and additional recreational activities – create a multiplier effect, attracting a wide range of local entities to economic activity. This contributes to the development of small businesses, increasing employment and expanding local value chains, particularly through the sale of products and trophy processing. An important component is also the receipts to local budgets from administrative fees and licenses, which strengthen communities' financial bases. Thus, commercial hunting tourism forms a diversified income model, within which direct financial revenues, the development of entrepreneurship and the stimulation of related sectors of the economy are combined.

Therefore, commercial hunting tourism can serve not only as an additional source of income for rural communities but also as a tool for the structural transformation of the local economy in the context of post-war recovery, thereby strengthening their financial autonomy and sustainability. This necessitates the development of a holistic strategic approach (table 6).

Table 6

Strategy for the development of commercial hunting tourism in rural territorial communities of Ukraine

Stage		
Content of measures	Expected result	Impact on the financial sustainability of the community
1. Diagnostic		
Inventory of hunting grounds, assessment of the security environment, demand analysis and identification of subjects	Determination of the real resource and market potential of the community	Minimization of risks of ineffective management decisions
2. Institutional and regulatory		
Formation of operating rules, establishment of transparent tariffs, implementation of control mechanisms, interaction with local self-government bodies	Legalization and institutional regulation of activities	Increase in stability and predictability of revenues
3. Infrastructure		
Development of transport accessibility, navigation, digital services, hunting bases, security measures and accommodation	Formation of an attractive tourist environment	Activation of local economic activity
4. Product and service		
Development of comprehensive service packages (hunting, accommodation, food, transport, recreation)	Formation of a competitive hunting tourism product	Increase in average income per visitor
5. Marketing		
Promotion, cooperation with tour operators and branding of the territory	Increase in tourist flow	Expanding the community's income base
6. Social and environmental		
Compliance with extraction limits, biodiversity monitoring, community involvement and implementation of social responsibility principles	Ensuring a balance of economic and environmental effects	Formation of long-term income stability
7. Financial and effective		
Monitoring of income, budget revenues, employment and local added value	Evaluation of the effectiveness of the implemented model	Strengthening the financial autonomy of the community

Source: created by the author

The proposed strategy provides for the phased development of commercial hunting tourism as a component of the local economy of rural territorial

communities. Its implementation ensures a coordinated combination of the resource potential of hunting grounds, tourist infrastructure, service activities and budgetary mechanisms into a holistic system of income generation. In contrast to the fragmented use of hunting resources, the strategic approach is focused on creating a multi-channel economic impact, manifested in increased local budget revenues, expanded employment, the development of small businesses, and strengthened financial stability of communities. At the same time, the phased implementation allows for the consideration of security, environmental and institutional constraints, ensuring the model's adaptability to the conditions of post-war recovery.

Conclusions. The Ukrainian hunting economy, despite losses from military actions, retains resource and institutional potential, creating the prerequisites for its further development. At the same time, the presence of a significant resource base does not yield the desired economic impact without the development of infrastructure and integration into the tourism market. The revival of administrative activity and the growth of budget revenues confirm the trend towards the sector's recovery; however, its efficiency can increase significantly if it is transformed into a commercial tourism product. This will allow the formation of a multi-channel income system and create a multiplier effect on the local economy, thereby strengthening the financial autonomy of rural territorial communities. The proposed phased approach will ensure the systematic use of the industry's potential in the conditions of post-war recovery.

Prospects for further research include developing methodological approaches to assessing the economic effects of hunting tourism and its impact on the financial stability of territorial communities.

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